

Disease resistance

Screening of rice varieties and lines against stem rot in Bangladesh

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To isolate and identify sources of resistance to stem rot of rice caused by *Sclerotium oryzae* Catt. (*Leptosphaeria salvinii* [Catt.] Kr & Web), 1,005 varieties and lines collected from the BRR germplasm bank and advanced breeding lines were screened during 1978 boro, aus, and T. aman seasons in BRR fields.

One-month-old seedlings were transplanted at 25- x 20-cm spacing in 2-m single rows. A check variety, Iratom-38 or TN1, was planted after every 10 entries and on both ends of every block. Fertilizer was applied at 90:67.5:45 kg/ha (urea in 2 splits) and the rows were weeded. The levees surrounding the nursery plot were raised and plastered with mud to maintain at least 7-10 cm standing

Summary of results of screening rice varieties and lines against stem rot at BRR, Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh, 1978.

Season	Varieties, lines screened (no.)	Varieties and lines (no.) with disease score ^a of			
		0	0.1-3.0	3.1-6.0	6.1-9.0
Boro	78	0	19 ^b	58	1
Aus	429	0	53 ^c	334	42
T. aman	498	0	9 ^d	428	61

^a0 = immune, 0.1-3.0 = resistant to moderately resistant, 3.1-6.0 = intermediate, 6.1-9.0 = susceptible to highly susceptible.

^bIncludes B5441b-Kn-7-1-2-3, BG375-1(75-404), BR8, Chandrasail 1, Chainung-Sen-yu-6, DJ684D, IR32, IR944-85-1-2-1-1-2-1, IR2071-586-5-6-4, IR2451-90-4-3, IR2793-80-1, and IR3464-75-1-1.

^cIncludes B441bl26-2-3-1-9, B462B-Pn-1-3, Baspati, BR6, BR161-2B-42, BR168-2B-23, BR1031-48-1-2, C168, Chakila, Chandina, Chandrasail 1, Giza, B541b-Kn-19-3-4, IR2071-625-1, BG11-11, BG35-2, BR2-29-2-1-3, BR3-12-B-15-54, BR4-30-3-2-1, BR4-30-51-2, BR9-17-4-1, BR13-47-3, IET5107, IR2061-214-3-3-32, and IR2061-214-3-14.

^dIncludes BR4-30-3-2-1, BR52-87-1/HR90, BR52-87-1/34, IR2031-2384-1-3-2, Purbachi, Remadja, Tan I x Ta-Poo-cho-Z, Badaia chikon, and BR4.

irrigation water. At the late tillering stage plants were inoculated with *S. oryzae*. Sclerotia and mycelia were prepared in an autoclaved 2:1 rice hull: rice grain mixture and spread over the center of the rows at 20 ml/row. Infection on the outer leaf sheath became visible 2 weeks after inoculation.

At maturity 3 to 4 hills from the center of each row were cut down to soil level, and then 25 random tillers were graded individually on a disease index scale of 0-9, based on depth of infection and severity. The average reading from the 25 tillers was considered the index for the variety (see table). ■

Insect resistance

Resistance of paddy varieties to gall midge

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Epidemics of the paddy gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* occurred in 1971, 1972, 1975, 1976, and 1978 in the rice bowl of Chattisgarh, Madhya Pradesh. Early, medium, late, and resistant groups of tall and semidwarf paddy were therefore screened for reaction to gall midge in government farms and cultivators' fields.

In the early group susceptibility to silver shoots ranged from 0.7 to 41%

Reaction of transplanted varieties to gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* in 1978 kharif. Raipur, India.

Designation	Tillers (av no./hill)	Panicles (%)	Silver shoots (%)	Yield (t/ha)
<i>Early</i>				
R155-2598	5.1	96.4	0.7	4.2
R155-355	12.2	47.4	40.9	3.6
JR16-15-1-1	7.2	75.6	3.7	2.8
JR16-15-1-1 ^a	29.7	38.9	22.3	1.5
Anjania ^a	4.3	49.6	13.4	2.3
Kaveri	6.8	72.2	14.5	3.7
Anupama	5.8	86.2	9.1	4.5
<i>Medium</i>				
Kranti	9.7	40.1	28.6	3.3
Garima	15.6	36.5	45.6	4.0
Pragati	14.4	44.3	35.0	4.0
Madhuri	14.1	45.7	26.1	2.4
R2270	13.1	59.8	29.2	3.1
Assamchuri	17.8	47.0	20.4	3.9
TN1	8.7	79.5	17.6	4.5
R8-2535	12.4	73.3	6.2	6.1
Ratna	5.6	63.3	31.4	3.1